

DEVELOPING INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION SKILLS OF PRE SCHOOL EDUCATION TEACHERS.

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Annotation. Develop an understanding of your own cultural background and biases, as well as those of others. This can help you navigate differences and build connections with people from diverse backgrounds. Active Listening: Practice active listening skills to truly understand and empathize with others' perspectives, beliefs, and experiences. This can help you communicate effectively and respectfully across cultures. Open-Mindedness: Approach interactions with an open mind and a willingness to learn from others. Be curious and ask questions to deepen your understanding of different cultural norms and values.

Key words: Cultural awareness, active listening, open-mindedness, adaptability, empathy, cultural sensitivity, continuous learning.

Аннотация. Развивайте понимание своей собственной культурной среды предубеждений, а также предубеждений других. Это может помочь вам преодолеть различия и наладить связи с людьми из разных слоев общества. Активное слушание. Практикуйте навыки активного слушания, чтобы по-настоящему понимать и сопереживать точкам зрения, убеждениям и опыту других людей. Это может помочь вам эффективно и уважительно общаться между представителями разных культур. Открытость: подходите к взаимодействию непредвзято и с готовностью учиться у других. Будьте любопытны и задавайте вопросы, чтобы углубить понимание различных культурных норм и ценностей.

Ключевые слова: культурная осведомленность, активное слушание, непредвзятость, адаптируемость, сочувствие, культурная чувствительность, непрерывное обучение.

In today's diverse and multicultural society, it is crucial for pre-school education teachers to possess strong intercultural communication skills. These skills are essential for effectively engaging with students from various cultural backgrounds, fostering a sense of inclusivity and understanding, and promoting a positive learning environment. In this article, we will explore the importance of developing intercultural communication skills in pre-school education teachers and provide practical strategies for enhancing these skills.

Why are Intercultural Communication Skills Important?

Pre-school education teachers play a critical role in shaping young children's attitudes, beliefs, and behaviors. By developing strong intercultural communication skills, teachers can create a welcoming and inclusive classroom environment where all students feel valued and respected. This, in turn, can lead to improved academic performance, social-emotional development, and overall well-being among students.

Additionally, in today's globalized world, it is essential for educators to be able to effectively communicate with individuals from diverse cultural backgrounds. By honing their intercultural communication skills, pre-school education teachers can bridge cultural divides, break down stereotypes, and promote cross-cultural understanding and cooperation.

Practical Strategies for Developing Intercultural Communication Skills

1. Self-Reflection: Pre-school education teachers should take the time to reflect on their own cultural beliefs, biases, and assumptions. By examining their own cultural identity and values, teachers can better understand how these factors may influence their interactions with students from different cultural backgrounds.

2. Cultural Competence Training: Schools and educational institutions should provide training and professional development opportunities for pre-school

education teachers to enhance their cultural competence. This may include workshops, seminars, and courses on topics such as cultural awareness, sensitivity, and communication.

3. Building Relationships: Teachers should make an effort to build positive relationships with students, families, and colleagues from diverse cultural backgrounds. By actively listening, showing empathy, and demonstrating respect for cultural differences, teachers can create a sense of trust and rapport that fosters effective communication.

4. Encouraging Diversity: Pre-school education teachers should incorporate diverse perspectives, experiences, and resources into their curriculum and teaching practices. By exposing students to a variety of cultural traditions, languages, and customs, teachers can promote intercultural understanding and appreciation.

5. Seeking Feedback: Teachers should seek feedback from students, families, and colleagues on their communication style and effectiveness. By soliciting input from others, teachers can identify areas for improvement and make adjustments to enhance their intercultural communication skills.

Cultural Awareness: Develop an understanding of your own cultural background and biases, as well as those of others. This can help you navigate differences and build connections with people from diverse backgrounds. **Active Listening:** Practice active listening skills to truly understand and empathize with others' perspectives, beliefs, and experiences. This can help you communicate effectively and respectfully across cultures. **Open-Mindedness:** Approach interactions with an open mind and a willingness to learn from others. Be curious and ask questions to deepen your understanding of different cultural norms and values.

Adaptability: Be flexible and adaptable in your communication style to accommodate different cultural preferences and communication norms. Pay attention to non-verbal cues, tone of voice, and body language.

Empathy: Cultivate empathy by putting yourself in the shoes of others and considering their feelings, experiences, and perspectives. This can help you build trust and rapport with individuals from different cultural backgrounds.

Cultural Sensitivity: Be mindful of cultural differences and avoid making assumptions or generalizations about individuals based on their cultural background. Respect diversity and treat others with dignity and respect.

Continuous Learning: Commit to ongoing learning and self-improvement in the area of intercultural communication. Seek out opportunities for training, workshops, and resources to enhance your skills and knowledge in this area.

Intercultural communication is the idea of knowing how to communicate in different parts of the world. Intercultural communication uses theories within groups of people to achieve a sense of cultural diversity. This is in the hopes of people being able to learn new things from different cultures. The theories used give people an enhanced perspective on when it is appropriate to act in situations without disrespecting the people within these cultures; it also enhances their perspective on achieving cultural diversity through the ideas of intercultural communication.

Many people in intercultural business communication argue that culture determines how individuals encode messages, what medium they choose for transmitting them, and the way messages are interpreted.^[1] With regard to intercultural communication proper, it studies situations where people from different cultural backgrounds *interact*. Aside from language, intercultural communication focuses on social attributes, thought patterns, and the cultures of different groups of people. It also involves understanding the different cultures, languages and customs of people from other countries.

Learning the tools to facilitate cross-cultural interaction is the subject of cultural agility, a term presently used to design a complex set of competencies required to allow an individual or an organization to perform successfully in cross-cultural situations.

Intercultural communication plays a role in social sciences such as anthropology, cultural studies, linguistics, psychology, and communication studies. Intercultural communication is also referred to as the base for international businesses. Several cross-cultural service providers assist with the development of intercultural communication skills. Research is a major part of the development of intercultural communication skills. *Intercultural communication* is in a way the 'interaction with speakers of other languages on equal terms and respecting their identities'.

Identity and culture are also studied within the discipline of communication to analyze how globalization influences ways of thinking, beliefs, values, and identity within and between cultural environments. Intercultural communication scholars approach theory with a dynamic outlook and do not believe culture can be measured nor that cultures share universal attributes. Scholars acknowledge that culture and communication shift along with societal changes and theories should consider the constant shifting and nuances of society.

Two women communicating beyond language

The study of intercultural communication requires intercultural understanding. Intercultural understanding is the ability to understand and value cultural differences. Language is an example of an important cultural component that is linked to intercultural understanding.

In conclusion, developing intercultural communication skills is essential for pre-school education teachers to create inclusive learning environments, promote cross-cultural understanding, and effectively engage with students from diverse backgrounds. By engaging in self-reflection, cultural competence training, relationship-building, diversity promotion, and feedback-seeking, teachers can enhance their intercultural communication skills and make a positive impact on the lives of their students. Communicating in practice: Foreign language teachers give

students the opportunity to practice communication. It helps students develop communication by practicing learning, communicating with others, and giving each other a guide to express themselves.

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